

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF LAPTOP AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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Introduction:

“Laptops aided students in becoming better writers in general, not just better writers while using laptops.”

A last decade Meant for technology, plenty of new technical devices came into the force, especially in the area of Communication. In the above devices pioneer one is computer. It took up the human beings in to the next level. But the important thing in the computer is it is big, it is need wires, connectivity, separate rooms. The person should sit in front of computers to do the work, so if we need a work we have to reach the computer where it is locate. To remove these practical difficulties technical intellectuals found Lap top. Lap top is a “Portable and compact personal computer with the same capabilities as a desktop computer. Laptop computers have an L-shape design and the screen can be lowered and closed to allow for easy transportation of the machine ”. Important laptop is very wide and versatility in nature. We can use it for business, education, monitor and entertainment too. It saves time and Money of human beings. In this context we are going to find the role of laptop in Student’s day to day life. In the educational Point of view the see the laptop is an opportunity for more innovative teaching, and it is increasing student attention during class hours. But sometimes in teacher’s point of view, Laptop is disturbing in middle of the classrooms. But ultimately laptops is an effective tool for student learning but the important thing is in the hands lecturers to plan carefully for how and when they will ask students to use their laptops .

Statement of the Problem

Laptop both positive and negative impacts. On the positive side, it is informative, gaining knowledge, easy to store, reducing time, easy to transfer, presentation, golden tool in learning process. Additional functions like take notes, drawings, animations. Especially laptop promoting learning freely. In negative aspect side , instead of learning , if students are prefer entertaining and fun oriented activities , It will spoil class room atmosphere , watching films , postures sometimes it is moves to anti social activities too. The technology is a knife, the thing is How we use that, Tamilnadu government provides free laptop for students, now a day’s most of the students step in to the college with laptop due to the government policy. So it seems usage laptop is high in modern days. In this it is very essential to study about impact of Laptop’s among college students in Coimbatore district , when , where , why , how , to whom they are using , whether using for informative or fun making , influencing factors etc.

Objectives of the study

The present study aims at analyzing the Impact of laptop among the college students in Coimbatore district. The following are the objectives drawn to fulfill the aim of the study.

- To study about the cultural, social, economic, educational and psychological factors that influences students towards Laptop.
- To identify the factors that determines the attitude towards laptop.
- To evaluate the experience of students in laptop.
- To evaluate the student satisfaction towards laptop using.

Research Methodology

The current study is both explorative and descriptive in nature.

Stage I: First stage of the research is exploratory by nature. Explorative research from part of desk work carried for collection of review of literature. This is done in two phases. The initial phase is to undertake detailed secondary data search about student behavior in India, student attitude and preferences and satisfaction towards among. This forms the desk research work where the reviews of available secondary literature for the study were collected. This exploratory search from the basis for preparing the questioner for the next stage.

Stage II: A descriptive research has been carried out at the second stage by applying a survey method. Filed survey form part of descriptive study that is a fact finding investigation with adequate interpretation. Questioner consists of four segments contains compete details on the socio-economic profile of the students, their behavior, factors influence's their attitude towards laptop in Coimbatore District.

Study Area

The current study is mainly concentrated on the leading colleges of Coimbatore, the third largest city of Tamil Nadu (the popular southern state of Indian sub-continent), one of the most educational and fastest growing cities in India, known as the intellectual capital of South India or the Manchester of the South, well known for its textile, auto ancillary, electric pumps & motors Schools, Colleges, Medical Institutions and various other engineering Institutions and industries. The city is situated on the banks of the river Noyal at the foot hills of Nilgiris, it is known for its pleasant climate, peaceful atmosphere, cosmopolitan outlook and Education. Thus, Coimbatore is selected as the study area.

Research Design

The researcher aims at analyzing the impact of laptop among the college students in Coimbatore District. The current study is both explorative and descriptive in nature.

Sample size :

It has been observe That in thèse 50 sample were chose for Survey.

As per the James H. McMillian (1996) a convenience sample is a group of subjects selected because of availability, often this is the only type of sampling possible especially in geographical area based study, where the target group

of population is only available for study, and the primary purpose of the research may not be to generalize but to better understand relationships that may exist. Similarly Roscoe (1975) proposed that a sample size of >30 and <500 are appropriate for most research. Based on this concept the sampling framework of the study is constructed.

For the study purpose, the samples of 50 College Students were selected for the study by using Convenience Random Sampling Method bases with the support of friends, relatives and references groups.

Sources of Data

Database of the study includes both primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected through individuals using a structured questionnaire. First-hand information has been collected from the College students.

The secondary data required for the study were collected from journals, published documents, and websites.

Scope of the Study

The purpose of the study is to know the impact of laptop among college students in Coimbatore district. In all institutions especially Educational Institutions in those predominantly deals with people. It deals with human beings at every stage. This comprehensive study will benefit a large spectrum of retailers, Entertainers, Educationalist, Employer, academicians and researcher in understanding the behavior of attitude of college students towards laptop.

Limitations of the Study

Utmost care and efforts have been taken by the researcher to avoid shortcomings in the process of collection and analysis of data in spite of the care taken the study is prone to some limitations, which are mentioned below

1. The study is confined to the viewpoint of College students of Coimbatore district only.
2. The results of the study may not be applicable to other places of the country.
3. Though the researcher takes adequate care to make the respondents express their views frankly and freely, some of the views expressed by them are biased in nature that may affect the findings of the study.

Findings:

- 64% of the respondents are male students. 54% of the respondents are coming under the category of the age below 20 years
- 58% of them rural area respondents. 80% of the people say laptop is necessary. Buying the laptop from government 48% .from shop 30%. On line stores 22%.
- Brand laptop usage is apple 34%. 84% of respondents using first hand laptop.
- 54 % respondents spending 2-5 hours in laptop. For Education purpose 48% of respondents are using.
- 46% of respondents are using for entertainment.48% of them like speed in Laptop.

Suggestions:

- Faculties and family provide the opportunities for the students to using laptop in effective manner.
- To give awareness' to the student's about the pros and cons of Laptop, Provide the materials which are closely relate with the system.
- Giving the task to be complete with the help of laptop, provide the high grade system for presentation.
- Allow the students to using laptop in free Zones, reduce the paper work.
- Education institutions are advised to implement the Internet Control access to avoid the unnecessary Websites within the premises of Institution.

Conclusion:

“Student with routine access to technology learn these basic skill faster & better when they have a chance to practice them using technology”

There is no doubt that Laptop is playing important role in students learning and enrichment. But the important thing is how we use that, we already state that lap top is a golden tool for learning process. In this research we came to know the more number of students are using laptop because of government schemes and awareness , and they are using for educational purpose , they said it makes their work simple , it looks like their third hand. Instead of sitting in front of the Television in this decade , Majority of college students presence in front of laptop in their leisure times, that is good signal for student's and society because “If television a babysitter, the internet is a drunk librarian who won't shut up” TV is provide available information , But internet provide needed information whenever we want.